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INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF DESIGN

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***Abstract.** Students' knowledge, skills, and competencies in the field of intellectual property rights—particularly regarding designers' property and non-property rights to their works, trademarks, trade names, and industrial designs—will enable them to protect their creations in the future.*

***Keywords:** globalization, intellectual property law, counterfeiting, copyright, Intellectual Property Center, work registration, civil law, liability, claim, specialized courts.*

In the context of globalization and the increasing engagement of countries in international economic relations, the protection of intellectual property rights is becoming a pressing issue. The instances of distribution of counterfeit (fake) products are on the rise.

It is estimated that around 20% to 40% of all goods and services sold globally are distributed through counterfeit methods. For instance, works of designers and fashion designers are copied and sold without their permission for personal profit, trademarks are used illegally, artists' works are duplicated without consent, and copies of images sourced from the internet are created and distributed. [1, p. 221]

Students at the National Institute of Fine Art and Design frequently raise the concern: “We are authors, but others are using our works without our permission. They post on social media under our names and even fulfill orders as if the works were commissioned by them. How can we stop this?”

During court proceedings, determining the authorship of a work is essential. According to current legislation, establishing authorship of a copyrighted work does not require official registration. That is, it is not mandatory to register a work with the Intellectual Property Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Once an author presents their work to persons outside their family, the work is considered public, and witness testimony is crucial for determining ownership in court. However, the opposing side may also present false witnesses. [2, p. 2378]

Registering a work with the Intellectual Property Center requires time, expertise, and funding. For a young author, it is often difficult to determine whether their work will have market value.

It is recommended that authors, particularly designers, register their works to facilitate the identification of the author and rights holder in the future. [3, p. 8] However, there are alternative methods: for instance, an author can take a photo with their work and email it to themselves. This method can serve as proof of ownership, as the internet preserves data about when the work was uploaded. [4, p. 3]

Another common student question is: “Which government authority should we contact to protect our copyright?” When copyright violations occur, legal restoration is typically carried out within the framework of civil law. That means the offender bears civil liability, and compensation may be awarded for both material and moral damages. To hold the offender accountable, a statement of claim must be submitted. If the author cannot write the claim, they are forced to hire a lawyer.

Legal services come with fees. For property-related claims, a state fee of 4% of the claim amount is required, but it cannot be lower than the minimum monthly wage. [5, p. 915]

When a court accepts a lawsuit, the author must determine the amount of damages caused by the offender. In copyright cases, this is challenging. Estimating and proving damages is complex, and it is difficult to determine the quantity of counterfeit products in marketplaces. Authors cannot physically visit every marketplace to investigate how many fake copies have been sold.

In most cases, authors hire a lawyer, which can cost between 3 to 4 million Uzbek soums. Therefore, it is advisable to pursue legal action only if the value of the claim exceeds these expenses. If the author wins in court, all legal costs are recovered from the offending party. However, in practice, collecting funds from the offender can be problematic. [6, p. 4]

This leads to another issue: Are judges sufficiently qualified in the field of copyright law? Currently, due to the relatively low number of copyright disputes, judges lack experience in this area.

For comparison, in Germany and the United Kingdom, there are specialized courts that handle intellectual property disputes. The German Federal Patent Court was established in 1961, indicating both the need and justification for such courts. Due to the high volume of cases, judges in those countries possess substantial expertise. [7, p. 28]

In February 2004, the European Commission proposed the establishment of a European Patent Court to handle disputes related to intellectual property law. [8, p. 50]

In February 2013, a specialized Court for Intellectual Property Rights was established within the arbitration court system of the Russian Federation. It handles not only patent disputes but also copyright cases.

Conclusion

There are numerous problems concerning intellectual property rights, particularly with regard to designers' property and non-property rights to their works, trademarks, brand names, and indications of origin. Teaching students intellectual property law equips them with the tools to defend their work.

The international community is decisively moving toward the integration and unification of intellectual property norms. In this process, Germany's experience can serve as a valuable model. Establishing specialized courts to resolve intellectual property disputes is an advisable step forward.

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